

THE CONTENT OF THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING READING COMPETENCIES IN FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article describes the issues related to the content of the process of development of reading competencies in future English language teachers. The process of forming the interest of future English language teachers in literary examples of elementary school through reading has its own specific stages, and as a result of the gradual organization of these stages, the process of forming students' interest in literary examples based on reading is effective.*

Keywords: *reading competencies, specific stages, concept, pedagogical process.*

INTRODUCTION

The idea, practical value of any activity, process and system depends on what principles it is based on. For this reason, priority principles, which take a leading place in its essence, are determined in planning the organization of activities, ensuring the flow of the process and forming the system. After all, the principles determine their gradual direction, and also take the form of order and rules. Therefore, during the period of conducting the research, special attention was paid to identifying the principles that are the priority in ensuring the effectiveness of the pedagogical process aimed at the formation of reading skills in primary school students.

Audio books can also be used to develop reading competencies in future English language teachers. After all, according to their psychological characteristics, children are divided into three groups:

1) auditory - those who remember well what they heard; 2) visualists - those who remember well what they saw; 3) kinesthetic people - those who remember well what they did. In addition, in the global information environment, the number of people who prefer to read audio books rather than print books is increasing. There are several advantages of reading audio books through a mobile phone or tablet. Because its use does not choose a particular place or address.

At the same time, it should be mentioned that, no matter how convenient it is to use audio books, their use also has certain disadvantages. In particular, electronic devices work on electricity, and being constantly under the influence of electricity is harmful to human health. In addition, "while listening to a book, the human mind does not focus on one place. Less is remembered without seeing the text. Such an experiment was carried out: the participants were invited to listen to audio books. They deliberately listened to the book without doing any other work in parallel. But they were still confused" [6].

DISCUSSIONS

Therefore, in our opinion, the use of audio books should not be the main tool used in pedagogical activities at other stages of the development of reading competencies of future English language teachers, it is necessary to use them from time to time to achieve "variety" of pedagogical activities and to interest students. Thus, the organization of pedagogical activities aimed at the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers in accordance with certain principles guarantees the achievement of the expected result. Corporate, purposeful, projective, layered, valuable, interactive, innovative and reflexive approaches, volunteer activities, taking age characteristics into account, visualization, consistency, continuity, systematicity, unity

of the lesson and extracurricular study, and such principles as diversity will be used in conducting the research. it was determined that it is of primary importance in the development of reading competencies in English language teachers.

Certain factors also influence the pedagogical process aimed at developing reading competencies in future English language teachers and ensure its effective passage. It was found that the impact of these factors is high when conducting research aimed at developing reading competencies in future English language teachers.

Formative experience was organized based on the principles and factors mentioned above. This is discussed in the next paragraph of the work.

Through theoretical analysis of scientific works related to the research problem, observation of pedagogical practice, analysis of the attitude of respondent-students involved in experimental work, teachers to the process, it was made sure that the following principles and approaches are of priority in the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers:

Table 1

The main principles and approaches to the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers

Principles	Approaches to the organization of activity
Corporate principle	Communicative approaches
The principle of cooperation (pedagogical mutual activity).	Person-oriented approaches
The principle of creativity	Orientation to subjective activity dialogic cultural-humanitarian approaches
Innovative principle	Interactive approaches
Project principle	Pragmatic approaches
A valuable principle	Reflexive approaches
The principle of cultural harmony	Cultural approaches
The principle of consistency, systematicity, continuity	Systematic-holistic approaches
The principle of taking age characteristics into account	Pedagogical (supportive) approaches

METHODS AND ANALYSIS

Below, the importance of the above-mentioned principles in the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers is briefly explained.

The corporate principle means that the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers, the promotion of reading ideas is a systematic, collective process that is carried out together, unanimously and cooperatively by the general secondary school community. According to him, each general secondary school has its own concept, general work plan, and on the basis of a single goal, it indicates that each class also operates on the basis of a guiding program that defines prospective tasks. It provides theoretical-methodological, organizational-technological and practical-methodical support in effectively applying the ideas of the referral program to pedagogical practice. The pedagogical team of the school will jointly analyze the factors of the achieved achievements and the existing shortcomings, and develop prospective projects for the next period (academic year) in mutual cooperation.

The objective principle indicates that short, medium and long-term pedagogical projects to develop reading competences in future English language teachers, to promote reading ideas, have a specific purpose of the pedagogical activities organized on the basis of the main, main goal. The organization of pedagogical activity according to the specific purpose provides an opportunity to ensure a systematic, consistent, orderly, uninterrupted process, reading books that develop reading competencies in future English language teachers, clarification of reading skills, qualifications, and evaluation of students' activities according to carefully based criteria.

The principle of creativity represents a carefully based project of the pedagogical activity process aimed at developing reading competencies in future English language teachers. In the period when the development of the projects is envisaged, the formation of students' reading, reading skills, qualifications, and then the development through prediction, planning, modeling and construction in a gradual (evolutionary) way will serve to increase the effectiveness of pedagogical activity. After all, taking into account existing factors (forecasting), systematically and step-by-step organization of activities (planning), formulating their contents (modeling) and putting theoretical ideas into practice (construction), achieving interdependence and connection between the structural elements of the whole system, internal capabilities into a single helps to concentrate.

A hierarchical approach to the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers is twofold: 1) literacy (reading and writing skills); 2) assumes an ownership approach to reading skills.

Group 1 will develop reading competencies in future English language teachers (reading of fiction books in this group will be organized by teachers, parents, librarians, volunteers, and small conversations will be organized);

The 2nd group will develop the reading competencies of the future English language teachers and ensure that they become a qualification (in this group, the reading of literary works will be achieved gradually by the students themselves; the participation of teachers, parents, librarians, volunteers in the book reading process will guide the students, help them choose books, will consist of joint discussion).

The valuable principle involves the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers, the formation of concepts about the social and personal importance of reading books, the fact that they are a source of pleasure for a person, as well as a resource that will be valued from time immemorial, learning to save books, and achieving the goal of making reading a daily habit.

An interactive approach means that in the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers, it is organized in cooperation with teachers, parents, librarians, and volunteers. Mutual cooperation in reading fiction books consists in reading the text of the work in turn (first one or two sentences, then two or three lines, and in the 3rd and 4th grades from the beginning of two or three lines), discussing the content of the work together, answering questions together, looking at the pictures of the heroes of the work. based on drawing, book repair, classroom library activities. In the course of the research, "Blitz-survey", "Cluster", "Consider all factors!", "Logical Confused Chain", "Siquain" and "Conceptual Jalval" interactive methods were effectively used.

The innovative principle refers to the organization of pedagogical activities aimed at developing reading competencies in future English language teachers with the help of advanced, non-traditional forms, methods, tools and technologies. The organization of pedagogical activity with the help of innovative forms, methods, tools and technologies creates interest and need for reading books in students and forms a positive attitude. Binary lesson, problem conversation,

virtual exhibition (organizational form), "Blitz survey", "Cluster", "Consider all factors!", "Logical tangled chain", "Sinquain" and "Conceptual table" (method), mobile phone, Internet, tablet (tool), as well as "Multi-part work", "Finish the fairy tale (story, poem)", "Fables based on questions", "My favorite poem", "Fable in picture" technologies were used appropriately and effectively.

A reflexive approach shows the need to develop reading competencies in future English language teachers, and parents and librarians should analyze the effectiveness of their activities in a certain period of time.

Voluntary approach (lat. "voluntarius" - volunteering) is a type of activity organized voluntarily, which involves the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers. It is known that social work is organized in educational institutions. Volunteering also has a double practical value as a type of socially beneficial activity. Firstly, it creates qualities such as social activity, self-awareness, self-confidence, self-esteem, generosity (helping others), communicativeness in students who volunteer, and secondly, the process aimed at developing reading competencies in future English language teachers. creates the necessary conditions for consistent, continuous and systematic implementation.

The principle of taking age characteristics into account allows for the correct selection of literary works for the development of reading competencies in future English language teachers. After all, according to age characteristics, for students of this educational age, it is necessary to choose artistic works of small size, interesting, decorated with pictures and bright colors, with a unique original form.

The principle of consistency, continuity, and systematicity ensures continuous and effective organization of pedagogical activities aimed at developing reading competencies in future English language teachers. Because, precisely on the basis of consistency, continuity, and systematicity, the process develops gradually, creating the necessary pedagogical conditions for the full use of the influence and opportunities of existing factors.

The unit of in-class and out-of-class reading activities aims to develop reading competencies in future English language teachers and to build reading skills in relation to each other. If, during the course of the lesson, the students' reading skills (accurate reading, fast reading, expressiveness of reading, reading comprehension skills) will be transformed into reading skills, as well as sharing the impressions of reading with others.

According to the age characteristics of visualization, elementary school students effectively receive information about social and natural existence through their eyes. Accordingly, in the process of developing the reading competence of future English language teachers, it is considered appropriate to cover the content and plot of the work based on pictures, posters, the work itself and the presentation along with reading the book. Consequently, visualization helps students of the appropriate age period to have a clear, complete perception of the reality of the work.

Diversity is the development of reading competence in future English language teachers, who have a stable focus, and at the same time, they are interested in receiving a lot of information in the form of text, images, and sounds. Therefore, it is not easy to "hold" their attention on a certain object at a certain time. The only way to achieve this goal is to bring interesting, colorful fiction to their attention. In cases where this is not the case, elementary school students have a positive attitude towards reading, reluctance to read books, and a decrease in interest is observed. For this reason, it is necessary to present colorful fiction literature in the development of reading competencies of future English language teachers, to achieve the organization of reading activities based on various forms, methods, tools, and technologies in the process of reading them.

According to pedagogue V.P. Ermakov, the use of tactile books in the educational process helps to bring visually impaired children closer to the scientific perception of the environment and enrich their artistic and social experiences [1].

In the course of the formative experiment, based on the study of information and library resources of bookstores and general secondary schools, it was witnessed that the following types of books for children of preschool and elementary school age are offered today by authors of fiction, publishers and trade networks:

Family reading. In its essence, "family reading is the conversation of parents with their children on moral topics based on the reading of fiction together with their children [5]. Interviews can be short or long depending on the nature, character, genre, and size of the selected work of art. In the course of the conversation, the task of adults is to achieve "the best, good family tradition that is organized together every day or at free time in the evening" [Ibid].

As in any process, the organization of family education leads to the expected result only under certain conditions. For this reason, it is necessary to provide methodical support to the parents of elementary school students in order to effectively start family education.

CONCLUSION

It can be noted that only when the process of communication with the book is organized based on the interests of the future English language teachers, the works of art will have an effective impact on their emotional world and facilitate their perception of reality.

Our observations have once again confirmed that color pictures and illustrations in books are of special importance in providing future English language teachers with an easy understanding of the content of works of art.

It is pedagogically important for future English language teachers to correctly choose books recommended for independent reading in the formation of interest in examples of fiction in future English language teachers. In this process, the teacher conducts individual interviews and questions with future English language teachers.

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